

PACIFICUS

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“RAINBOW OF DREAMS”

Rainbow of dreams, so colorful- And fancy at night!
Hues of promise glow and we're satisfied
Painting the way, the palette of education

Today and tomorrow, both bright and full of promise
A story is being told in every color and for each color a story.
Of minds grown young and old
Way of learning, arc of a rainbow
To lead students on, in their design of things.